

Grace Covenant Centre, Ado-Ekiti

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christianity, Pentecostal

Grace Covenant Centre, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria grew out of a Christian fellowship membered by some Christian staff of the then Ondo State University, Ado-Ekiti (OSUA) and other categories of civil servants who were resident in the town in the 1990s. The group initially held their meetings at the defunct Ajitadidun premises in the Adebayo area of the town before building their permanent site near their former meeting place. Before organizing this fellowship, the leader of the group, Pastor Felix Aderibigbe had successfully started and groomed the first Pentecostal Christian student fellowship in OSUA in 1984. Grace Covenant Centre was therefore the second Christian group organized by the visionary Christian leader who had previously been engaged in Christian fellowship leadership during his days as a student at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. Being one of the first Pentecostal fellowships in the town, Grace Covenant Centre soon began to attract young, educated and upwardly mobile Christian professionals, businessmen and women and civil servants in Ado-Ekiti. The church which is known for building disciples of Jesus Christ has grown from its Adebayo assembly to open at least three other branches in Ado-Ekiti township. Besides, it has grown through its evangelistic outreach arm to set up a few other branches in other towns in Ekiti State. It also has a branch each in neighbouring Ondo and Ogun States. Being a church made up of academicians, technocrats and top executives in public and private sector, many of its branches are located near university campuses or membered by members of the academic community. It has also organised campus fellowships in universities and other tertiary institutions in Ado-Ekiti and other towns. The fellowship has grown to become one of the most popular Pentecostal movements in the city of Ado-Ekiti. The church organises several special programmes and annual conventions. It holds a summer prayer school in June of every year. In this programme, members are taught the principles of strategic prayers and exposed to certain underlying issues that must be addressed by Christians to be victorious in all their endeavours. At some point each year (mostly in February), it celebrates a jubilee crusade. This is a time for proclaiming liberty to those oppressed by sin, Satan and the world's system. It celebrates its annual convention (Glory Conference) in the last full week of October. Members from the branches are encouraged to attend the annual convention which is usually power-packed. The church has built relationships with other Christian ministries and their leaders across the country. Leaders of such church ministries are often invited by the church to speak at their special programmes. As a faith community, the church emphasises love, fellowship and building strong horizontal and vertical relationships among members and with God through their Lord and saviour, Jesus Christ.

Date Range: 1990 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria, Ado-Ekiti

Grace Covenant Centre, Ado-Ekiti is located in the capital city of Ekiti State in the Yoruba speaking area of Nigeria. This region shows the approximate vicinity of Ado-Ekiti.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/new-features.php>
- Source 1 Description: New King James Version of the Holy Bible. This is the primary religious text used in the church
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.africanportal.net/ABO/BibeliAtoka/>
- Source 2 Description: A section of the church membership relies on the use of the Yoruba version of the Holy Bible

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact the church has with other religious groups in the area is competitive. However, the church maintains a healthy relationship with other groups around.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is accommodating and pluralistic.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: There has been no history of violent conflicts of religious groups within the sample region

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Membership of the group by birth is only true as long as the children remain under the care and supervision of their parents who are members of the church. The church is a highly mobile assembly. This is because it consists of very educated members whose children travel across the globe and soon leave the city after completing their education. Such children join other churches after relocating from the city.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Although most of the members are well educated, the church accepts and has in its fold members with little or no education.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There is no age limit/barrier to attaining membership of the church

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: People who are joining the church are usually advised to attend a few weeks of foundational class otherwise called believers' class. In the few weeks of interaction, such individuals are taken through the elementary discussions around salvation, discipleship and other important topics in the Christian faith.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Though this is not unduly emphasised, religious professionals and leaders at different levels in the church are especially admonished to keep offering Christ's salvation to others who have not yet had an experience of the new life in Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates are considered as former members who have forsaken very vital aspects of the faith which the church considers as fundamental to their beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: The church does not consider itself to be in a position to punish apostates in any way or form. Members are admonished to pray for anyone who is viewed as having left their profession of faith and keep hoping that they will return to the fold of Christ in order to inherit eternal life in Christ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.5

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: Each local assembly has a leading figure among the class of leaders. The church is run by the inputs of all leaders while the superintending leader takes decisions in consultation with others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: Usually, the headquarter church in consultation with the local assemblies choose leaders who operate at the assembly level.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: It will be right to say that leaders at the headquarters of the religious group ratify the selection of leaders at the assembly level for the progress and smooth running of the branches.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: No political leader has any influence or role to play in the selection of leaders in the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers are usually offered to the supernatural being before a decision is made on the inclusion of individuals to the leadership of the church in any of its branches.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Usually, members do not make charges of fallibility on their leaders but this does not mean they the members do not hold their leaders as being above fault or mistakes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No one (members or leaders) is in the habit of laying charges of fallibility upon their leaders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: The church does not contravene the laws of their country. Therefore, no political leader has ever laid charges of fallibility upon the leadership of the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The church beliefs in the infallibility of the Holy Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Such stories as are associated with the Holy Bible are generally held in the church

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the bible is the word of God as revealed to His holy prophets and messengers across the age and are for the guidance of the entire human race in the path of righteousness and holiness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that that the Holy Bible is inspired by God.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
– No

Notes: The church believes that the Holy Bible is inerrant and infallible. Therefore, it is unalterable.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: There are no monumental religious architecture in the group. The church has built auditoriums for meeting purposes across their branches which meet the needs of each local assembly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is iconography present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: The church does not have sites dedicated to sacred practices in the strict sense although it expects that people attending their meetings conduct themselves properly and be respectful of the fact that their God is present at all of their meetings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit is conceived of as having an existence that outlasts the human body.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Though the church holds that the human spirit is conceived of as intangible, nevertheless, it is real and held as the essence of human existence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Notes: The theology around the afterlife in the church is well developed and clear. The church holds that the afterlife each of their members expects to have is above in the sky having God as the king and controller of all its affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Notes: The theology around the afterlife in the church is well developed and clear. The church holds that the afterlife that is prepared for disobedient and ungodly is below in the belly of the earth. Such individuals will be there suffering eternally with Satan and his demons.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The church does not believe in the doctrine of reincarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The church conducts formal burial/internment for their departed members

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The church respects the last wishes of members regarding their final burial places. Such decisions may be known to the church prior to the death of the member. In the absence of this, the decision of the families of members will be final on the burial site of their departed ones. This may be in the cemeteries or any other place so decided.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the decision of the deceased prior to their demise or that of the family in the event that they were not specific on their preferred burial site before death.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: This is not common among the congregation. However, should this be the choice of anyone or their family, the church is not likely to reject such wishes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are present in the church belief system. God is at the peak of this structure. His word (Christ) and His Spirit (the Holy Spirit) share the summit of the structure with God while angels and other heavenly beings make up the list of supernatural beings acknowledged by the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– Yes
Notes: The supreme high God which the church follows is perceived as one who lives in the skyey heaven.
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No
Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god is not equal to any other being. He is in a class of his own and so no leader of the church can be fused with him.
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes
Notes: All humans are held as the manifestation of the supreme high god in the theology of the church.
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– Yes
Notes: The church holds the view that the supreme high god is unquestionably good. They believe that in him is no evil whatsoever.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– Yes [specify]: The church holds that the supreme high god is omnipotent and omnipresent.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
– Yes
Notes: The church holds that all of the knowledge in this world emanates from the supreme high god. His knowledge is therefore not restricted to any single domain of human existence. His knowledge is pervasive on the earth.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Since his is perceived as an omnipresent god, the church holds that the supreme high god can see all humans everywhere normally visible or in places considered hidden to other beings.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The church conceives of the supreme being as the discerner of the mind and the intents of the heart as recorded in the bible. He therefore can see inside the heart, mind and no hidden motive is kept from him.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that by his nature the supreme high god knows the basic character of all humans.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The church holds the supreme being as the fountain of knowledge and so all knowledge including those hidden to men are known to him. In fact all knowledge in the known and extra terrestrial world emanate from him.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god is the ultimate rewarder of the actions of all humans. He rewards the good deeds and punishes the wrong deeds of the human race.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that all actions are sanctioned by the supreme high god. He is seen as the originator and the uncaused cause of all actions.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god exhibits negative emotions as a natural response to the disobedience of members of the human race. He could express anger, vengeance or regret for granting favours to ingrates.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that the supreme high god does not have hunger for food but could exhibit hunger for repaying both the good and evil deeds undertaken by humans.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: The church holds that the supreme high god recompenses the actions of all mortals, he meets all their needs gives rain and sunshine to the earth.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high god reveals himself to the church members in dreams and directs them in their actions.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Some members of the church especially their religious specialists report instances of trances where they have special encounters with the supreme being. This is towards having better life outcomes.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The church upholds prayers as a means of obtaining favours from the supreme being. One of their weekly meetings is entirely devoted to prayers (divining from the supreme being).

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The church accepts that the supreme being speaks with their members through the bible and other circumstances.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: The church holds that previously human spirits are not reckoned in the list of active beings (natural or supernatural)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: These include angels and other heavenly beings on the one hand and Satan and his demons on the other

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that God is the only supernatural being with unrestricted knowledge of affairs in this world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to specific areas within and outside the sample region. The church holds that even Satan the arch-enemy of the saints can only be in a particular place at every point in time. This accounts for his manner of response in the story of Job where he responded to God that he had been going to and fro the earth. He will not be privy to information or knowledge in places where he is not physically present

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that non-human supernatural beings can see humans everywhere normally visible (in public) especially when they have been sent to such individuals (for good or for evil). It is the non-human supernatural beings who work with God who are usually sent to accomplish good things on behalf of individuals while the non-human supernatural beings who answer to Satan usually work to harm or terrify humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden

motives):

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings especially those who are engaged with Satan thrive on the information humans release to them. They do not really have an understanding of what an individual is thinking. They wait for humans to express their frustrations or their state of mind so as to know how to attack or relate with the information they have obtained.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are aware of human actions and conduct and so can determine the basic character or personal essence of humans.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings may only guess and anticipate the actions of humans. The good ones anticipate that humans do good and follow the right path in life while the evil ones put stumbling blocks in the way of humans so they could fall off the right path and become doomed to eternal punishment like themselves.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

–Yes [specify]: The church believes that non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world. For example, they hold that Satan has more than 6000 years experience of dealing with humans. He is got all the tricks to engage humans and make them disobey God. Only those who rely on the supernatural strength provided by God would be able to overcome him and his other non-human agents.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The church believes that only God, the supreme being has deliberate causal efficacy in the world. According to the church, no other being is capable of causing or effecting a cause if it has not been allowed, permitted or sanctioned by God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: According to the church, non-human supernatural beings do not have indirect causal efficacy in the world. Only the supreme being does. Often, the possibility of a cause of action must have been allowed, permitted or sanctioned by the supreme being with the willingness of human agents who cooperate to bring those actions to effect. However, the part played by non-human supernatural beings may be to urge human agents on, encourage, deceive or confuse them to make those events occur. However, humans are inexcusable when such actions are brought to being because they had a part they played in the whole series of events through their self-will.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the non-human supernatural beings exhibit positive emotions like expressing joy, excitement and satisfaction among others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the non-human supernatural beings exhibit negative emotions like expressing disappointment, sadness and anger among others.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The kind of hunger these supernatural beings are assumed to exhibit in the understanding of the church includes hunger for carrying out their assigned roles and assignments, hunger to please and implement the mandates of their master (God or Satan, depending whether they are good or evil supernatural beings)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: There a whole lot of other features these supernatural beings are assumed to exhibit in the understanding of the church. These include benevolence, vengeance etc

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There are two kingdoms which the church recognises. The kingdom of light and that of darkness. God superintends over the kingdom of light while Satan superintends over the kingdom of darkness. Each of these kingdoms has its classes of supernatural beings. In the kingdom of light, angels and other heavenly beings operate as non-human supernatural beings while demons and other fallen angels are members of the class of supernatural beings who populate the kingdom of darkness.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed in the group that there are layers or categorization of the heavens where the spirits/supernatural beings operate. The higher the rank of the spirit, the higher the layer of heaven they operate from. They believe that angels are organised in ranks under superior or arch angels etc.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: It is believed in the church that supernatural beings are interested in the conduct of humans as it relates to adherence to prosocial norm adherence.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Food:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Sacred space(s):
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that sacred objects like the Holy Bible and other sacred objects and church grounds should not be desecrated or used for unholy activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The church holds that supernatural beings care about the whole aspects of human existence and how humans live their lives whether they conform to divine instructions in their speech, actions and meditations of their hearts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed in the church that supernatural beings care about murder of all humans. No one is permitted to take the life of another being either within or outside their religious community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed in the church that supernatural beings care about murder of all humans. No one is permitted to take the life of another being either within or outside their religious community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: It is believed in the church that supernatural beings care about murder of all humans. No one is permitted to take the life of another being either within or outside their religious community or those of other polities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery is forbidden to members of the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that incest is a taboo and should never be practised by any member of the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Premarital and extra-marital sexual relations are prohibited among members of the church. The church also frowns at humans having sexual relations with animals, as well as same sex marriage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that supernatural beings care about lying.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: The church frowns at all forms of fighting as they believe the supernatural beings disapproves of fighting.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that risks are to be approached reasonably and responsibly while actions involving risks are to be undertaken with care

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds the injunction that "you shall not covet your neighbour's property" very seriously.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual observances like praying, attending religious meetings and performing other duties relating to the faith of members are emphasised in the church. These are components of their faith which contribute to the spiritual growth of members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme being cares about performance of rituals. The church encourages members to attend religious meetings and participate in rituals as often as possible.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the church are discouraged against the use of unjust weights and insincerity in economic activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The church believes that supernatural beings care about the whole aspects of human existence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group holds the high god as the ultimate one who punishes the wrongs of all mortals. However, other supernatural beings assist him in the discharge of this task.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that cause and effect principles are also instrumental in apportioning punishment to wrongdoers. They believe that the supreme being deploys the cause and effect principle to both punish evil and reward the good deeds among mortals.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church acknowledges the roles played by the country's legal system in apportioning punishment for wrongs done. It also believes that by all means, no one deserving of punishment will escape it in the long run. All elements of nature will work to ensure every mortal gets punished for their wrong doing.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Group norms in the church is not restricted or narrowly applied to the assembly alone. By group norms, the church thinks of the general Christian norms as enunciated in the Holy Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: The church believes that there is a specific reason why every punishment is meted out to deserving individuals by the supernatural beings. Punishment is not just meted out at random.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, the church believes that punishments are also meted out to descendants of people who lived a life of disobedience to the supreme being especially those who committed some grievous offenses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that access to pleasures would be denied those who are faced with eternal punishment in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that those consigned to eternal punishment in the afterlife would suffer the terror and hurt of extreme and unending fire, poisonous insect infestation among other ills.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the range of punishments available to those consigned to everlasting punishment in the afterlife is simply endless. All forms of extreme pain, anguish and sorrow awaits those who will partake in punishment in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Since the supreme being abhors all forms of disobedience to divine instructions, the church holds that when humans contravene divine instructions, they fail to curry the favour of the supreme being. The church therefore holds that such disobedient folks would experience bad luck because the supreme being is refusing to listen to them and help them out with their requests.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Just as the Israelites suffered political failure in the days of the Christ because of their sins, many political failures are in this age and time considered as fall out of sin by the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that life itself is a battle. Defeats in the battles of life are therefore considered as punishments in this life.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Natural disasters like cyclones, earthquakes, landslides etc are seen as punishments upon humanity in this life by the church.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: The church considers all disasters including those on journeys as results of punishments on the human race.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that sensory displeasures could result from disobedience to divine instruction. They hold that any form of mishaps and distress are possible to humans undergoing spells of punishment from supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Barrenness and congenital abnormalities are seen occasionally as punishment

for disobedience to divine instruction in the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church rationalises that death is the end result of sin. So when someone considered to have contravened divine instruction is visited with death, it could be rationalised that such occurrence is a divine punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: This is another way the divine being ensures supernatural rewards/punishments to be effected.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: The church holds that upon admission into heaven, humans will be like angels and would not be restricted by the limitations they encountered as humans. This form of existence is not considered as reincarnation but just another form of existence in a realm different from that of the earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Though the church believes that there is an existence in a superior realm in the afterlife but it does not accept that this existence is a form of reincarnation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that existence in then afterlife is characterised by manifold pleasures and rewards. It is a life of bliss and immense enjoyment. The pleasures of a nice and serene environment, flowing rivers and the joy of beholding the presence of the supreme being are some of the other pleasures available to those who will inherit the afterlife with the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that all forms of rewards are accruable to those who follow divine instructions in this realm of existence. This includes political success and peace within the domain of those who follow divine instructions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Though the church does not engage in physical battles, it holds that life itself is a series of battles and so success in every aspect of life is seen as a reward from the divine being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds the saying of the Bible that "with long life will I (God) satisfy you (those who are obedient to divine instruction)" to be true. So enhanced health is a reward accruable to those who follow the path prescribed by the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The rewards accruable to those who follow the path prescribed by the church in this life are manifold. Some of those specific ones outside of those already identified include enjoying a peaceful and crisis-free life, finding favour with all men, enjoying success in all their endeavours etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The church recognises that the messiah has had his first visit to the earth. He is said to have returned to heaven to prepare a place for the believers who will be with him forever in homes he is currently preparing for them. His time of return is however unspecified and unknown to the people.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the messiah came to mediate between God and humans. The messiah is accepted by the religious group as one who came to restore humans back to a cordial relationship that existed between. He is seen to have come to destroy the works of the enemy of the soul of men; Satan.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: No, the group sees the messiah as a spiritual messiah who came to mend the broken walls of spirituality of the human race. He came to help the human race chart their way back to God.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The messiah's ultimate purpose is to restore the broken relationship between God and men. However, his coming is also seen as having activated the prospects of the experience of all other good things for the human race.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Though the church holds that eschaton is imminent, its exact time of occurrence is unknown. They believe that it will happen in this human age and in the lifetime of a generation of humans (it may be this generation or another).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: The church tends to believe that the time of the eschaton is at an unspecified time in the near future. This near future has been conceived about 2000 years ago and each generation of the Christian family the church belongs to has held that the eschaton is in a time in the near future. Not minding its seeming delay, the church has not changed its mind on its definition of the time of its imminent occurrence.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the messiah mandates that they (and other groups of Christians) preach to the entire human race about the kingdom the messiah came to earth to represent. Once this is done, they believe that the end of time (the return of the messiah) would come.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The church believes that there would be a divine judgement as part of the events of the end time. They hold that this judgement would be fair and would be devoid of injustice.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that there would be a restoration of the world to its original form (a form it assumed before it was infested with sin) during the period of the end time. It would be a time when anguish, pain, evil and all forms of diseases would be eliminated from the world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the time when peace would be restored on the earth (millennial reign) would only last a millennium after which Satan would be let loose again to deceive human kind once more to wage war against Christ. His army will be defeated and this event will precede the final judgement.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: The eschaton will mark the reign of Christ. This will be a theocratic government where the will of the supreme being reign without any hinderance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: After the initial seven-year reign of the Antichrist, theocracy will be the religious system that will be adopted during the eschaton. This will be at the Messiah's second coming to earth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: A select few who are able to endure the suffering and persecution of the Antichrist will survive the terror of the eschaton. The church holds that a a certain number of Israelites will be in this number.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The church does not encourage the group members to wait for the eschaton for their salvation. They admonish members to take advantage of the current opportunity

of grace to follow wholly the Christ and avoid a situation where they will have to endure the terror of the Antichrist in hope that they will pass through the coming suffering into eternal bliss.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: The church holds that those who will surrender to the reign of the Antichrist and fully accept the policies of his government will survive the eschaton. However, by their acceptance of all the policies of that government are consigned to eternal doom afterwards.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group prescribes general social norms for her members. These are not different from the norms and commandments sanctioned by the Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The church does not make distinctions between what it prescribes and what it practically permits or practices. Its conventions and moral distinctions are one and the same.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: Though the church is not involved in military campaigns, it admonishes her members to be brave as they traverse the earth. They are admonished to confront all their difficult encounters head-on with the strongest determination.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: The church encourages her members independence, creativity and freedom but urges that such freedom should never be seen as an opportunity to do wrong or disobey the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches the above virtues. It however instructs that the confidence of the members should be in God and not in themselves or in their finite powers and ability.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that the members should utilise their strength and deploy same in their daily tasks and not sit idly by or choose laziness above hard work. This, they hold will see them have their fortunes become bright and enviable.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: The religious group asks members not to be hungry for power or seek to acquire higher status to oppress other humans. They also teach the noble to be humble and kind to others without their privileges of birth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: The church appreciates beauty and attractiveness and accepts them as special gifts from the supreme being. However, it gently admonishes that members should not set their priority on them at the expense of their spiritual growth and development.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The religious group advocates several important virtues. Most of them have been identified in the section above. However, in addition to those identified, the church also encourages members to be helpful, forgiving, temperate etc.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches her members to follow strictly the forms of sexual relations which are in their view the types only accepted by bible standards. The other sexual relations they should refrain from include incest, bestiality and same sex marriage

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches her members to follow strictly the forms of sexual relations which are in their view the types only accepted by bible standards. The other sexual relations they should refrain from include incest, bestiality and same sex marriage

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Members of this religious group often give sacrificially from their possessions. They are taught that giving opens the windows of heaven to them and so makes them eligible to receive greater rewards of material and financial blessings from the inexhaustible storehouse of the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: The church teaches that the members give sacrificially to others outside the group as they also do to in-group members.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Destroyed:

– No

Notes: Members are never thought to destroy their properties as it is considered wasteful to destroy their possession.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Members of the group are taught to give to God to support the work of proselytising and kingdom expansion.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The ethical precepts upheld by the church are those recommended in the bible.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Families are encouraged to perform household rituals like praying together daily.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Notes: There are no stringent rules governing the time interval between the performances of rituals in members' household. However, families are enjoined to pray together daily preferably as the first engagement in the morning and last thing at night.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 10

Notes: Ten members may be considered as about smallest number of people who gather for large scale rituals. More than a thousand people could gather for some of the religious group's most important programmes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 36

Notes: At least three large scale rituals hold in each branch of the church weekly. These includes rituals held on Sundays, Tuesdays, Thursdays and sometimes on Fridays/Saturdays

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no extra-ritual in-group markers present in the religious group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Members refer to each other as brothers and sisters even though they are not related by blood.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: This religious group is within a multi-religious state. Multiple religious groups are allowed within the cities, towns and communities where branches of the church are located.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Though the church provides welfare packages to its members, there have not been any record of famine which necessitates the provision of famine reliefs in the communities where church operates.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: The church does not provide institutionalised poverty relief.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: The church does not run educational institutions where its members are trained. However, most members of the church are well educated and therefore have no problems sending their children to schools for the purpose of obtaining education.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the church obtain education at government and private owned educational institutions across the world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There are no formal bureaucracies within the church group.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the religious group interact with government bureaucracies and other forms of institutionalised bodies.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The availability of government water management schemes to members of the church is a function of the area within Nigeria where a branch of the church is located.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Most transportation infrastructure are private owned in Nigeria. The public transport system in the country is not reliable.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Group members are admonished to pay tithes in the church.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The national and sub-national governments of Nigeria levy taxes on individual members of the church as private citizens of the country.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group adherents interact with the Nigeria Police and recognise the constitutional duties of the Police Force.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with the Nigerian judicial system and recognises the constitutional duties of the body. Some members of the church are top members of the nation's judicial system. Some of them are senior lawyers while a few of them are judges within the nation's judiciary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Though the group's adherents are subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group its members are exceptionally law abiding. As such, there are no known records of any of its members coming under sanctions enforced by the legal system of

the nation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are subject to a formal legal code provided by the Nigerian State.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A few members of the church are members of the Police and other paramilitary forces in the country.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the branches of the church are in the Yoruba speaking area of the country. The church therefore uses the English language (Nigeria's lingual franca) and the Yoruba language as mediums of communication during their meetings and other forms of interactions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The choice of the use of the English language and Yoruba Language among members of the church is due to sociological factors in their environment. This is because the two languages are those in use in their locality.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Nigeria as a secular state uses the Gregorian calendar. The church also uses the calendar in planning her programmes and running her affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Members of the religious group buy their food from markets around them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria